

Influence of Programmes Differentiation on Performance of Private Universities in Kenya

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to analyze the influence of programmes differentiation on the performance of selected private universities in Kenya. The study adopted system theory, total quality management theory, balance Score Card theory, and Strategic Clock Model as the main theories and models of the study. The study targeted 18 Chartered Private Universities in Kenya. People to be targeted will be 245 Deans and Employees Working in Quality Assurance Departments of the 18 Chartered Private Universities in Kenya and 170 third and fourth year students in the 17 Chartered Private Universities. Further, the study will apply the sampling formula by Yamane (1967) to arrive at the 153 Deans and Employees Working in Quality Assurance Departments a sample size appropriate for the study. The number of students was arrived at through cluster sampling. Both the students and university employees will be subjected to questionnaires and interview guides. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data collected. Closed questions will be analyzed through the help of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer software by assigning numbers to responses for analysis of qualitative data, as it is efficient. Open ended questions were analyzed through percentages, frequencies, tables, and bar graphs. The inferential statistical method used in the study was a simple linear regression and analysis. The study established that the quality management system influenced the performance of private universities in Kenya.

Keywords: *University Performance, Competitive Strategy, Differentiation Strategy, International Standard Organization.*

1.0 Introduction

Differentiation strategy aims to build up a competitive advantage by offering unique products which are characterized by valuable features, such as quality, innovation, and customer service. Differentiation can be based on the product itself, the delivery system, and a broad range of other factors. With these differentiation features, firms provide additional values to customers who will reward them with a premium price (Hayward, 2006). Differentiation strategy is an approach under which a firm aims to develop and market unique products for different customer segments.

Raduan, Jegak, Haslinda, and Alimin (2009) further affirm that businesses that do things that are distinctive and difficult to replicate have a competitive advantage and are likely to be more profitable than its rivals. Factors such as strategic types, adoption of new technologies, quality products among others, have also been considered to have an important influence on the superior performance of firms. Over the years, business strategies have been found to have a direct influence on firms' competitiveness and growth performance (Sandlberg, 2010).

Differentiation is a business strategy where firms attempt to gain a competitive advantage by increasing the perceived value of their products or services relative to the perceived value of other firms' products or services. To implement these strategies successfully, organizations need to have an accurate view of the current competitive situation to persuade costumers about the features of the sustainable products (Pondeville, Swaen & de Rongé, 2013). According to Rahman et al. (2011), differentiation is a business strategy that seeks to build competitive advantage with its product or service by having it "different" from other available competitive products based on features, performance, or other factors not directly related to cost and price.

Private universities that succeed in a differentiation strategy often have access to leading scientific research, highly skilled and creative services and products. Also, there is a need for a development team, strong sales team with the ability to successfully communicate the perceived strengths of the services and products and corporate reputation for quality and innovation (Prescott, 2008). Successful differentiation is based on a study

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of buyers from different places needs and behaviour. Desired features are then incorporated into the services and products to encourage buyer preference for the services and products.

Kamau (2013) has examined the effects of differentiation strategy on sales performance in supermarkets in Nakuru town central business district. The purpose of the study was to establish the effects of differentiation strategy on the sales performance of supermarkets within Nakuru CBD. The study hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between product differentiation strategy adopted by retail supermarkets and sales performance. The study employed a non-experimental research survey design and used purposive and simple random sampling to get the sample size of the respondents. The findings of the study showed that product and physical differentiation play a major role in activating annual sales performance at the supermarkets. The study recommended that supermarkets should scale upon the attributes of the product and physical differentiation strategies if they are to compete in the growing market.

Shafiwu and Mohammed (2013) have investigated the effect of product differentiation on profitability in the petroleum industry in Ghana. The research sought to establish the relationship between differentiation and profitability in the petroleum industry and whether or not people patronized Effimax products. The research employed a correlation research design. It targeted 15 government owned and 14 privately owned oil marketing companies in Ghana. Cluster sampling technique was used to select one company out of the population. The study concluded that despite the fact that the petroleum industry is not seen to have differentiated products relative to other industries, it does not mean that the act of differentiation in itself is not a profitable strategy suitable to the industry. Rather, there may be other factors responsible for the less adoption. Shafiwu and Mohammed (2013) recommend the need to create awareness of the products.

Dirisu, Oluwule, and Ibidunni (2013) have studied product differentiation as a tool of competitive advantage and optimal organizational performance focusing on Unilever Nigeria. The study focused on how competitive advantage can be achieved through product differentiation strategy and, ultimately, on how it influences the performance of the organization in the manufacturing company. Survey research was adopted for the research because of the nature of the respondents. This entailed the administering of questionnaires to the chosen sample. The population of the respondents was rather large, made up of all customers/consumers of the products of Unilever Nigeria Plc. The analysis carried out proved the existence of a significant positive relationship between product differentiation and the sales growth of an organization. The study recommended that executive management ought to focus and invest more on product differentiation as it could be used as a major competitive advantage tool against competitors in the industry and it is capable of guaranteeing the long-term survival of the organization.

Finally, differentiation may be implemented by focusing on the linkage within or between firms, which includes linkage within functions of a firm, linkage with other firms, product mix, distribution channels, and service support. Ideally, the firm should differentiate itself along with several dimensions (Rothaermel, 2015). Differentiation may generate superior profitability for the reason that “[it] provides insulation against competitive rivalry because of brand loyalty by customers and resulting lower sensitivity to price. It also increases margins, which avoids the need for a low-cost position.

1.2 Private University Performance

The starting point for the ranking of universities and higher education institutions is normally regarded as the early 1980s when the U.S. News and World Report magazine published a ranking of American universities. The fact is, however, that the ranking of higher education institutions may be observed much earlier than this. Such institutions were already being classified in 1870 in the United States, and various rankings were subsequently performed sporadically throughout the 20th century (Shah & Swaminathan, 2008).

The first media ranking of universities and higher education institutions was published by the Chicago Tribune in 1957. However, the U.S. News and World Report’s rankings in 1983 and the Fiske Guide to Colleges in 1982 marked the start of considerably more extensive ranking activities in the higher education sector (Shah & Swaminathan, 2007). The ranking includes vetting the relative performance of academic programme or higher

education institutions against a set of objective criteria such as research output by the institution, number of students and perceptions from employers. The purpose of this process is to help students make informed decisions regarding their educational future by providing comparable information on the quality of higher education institutions (American Society of Quality, 2013). A tertiary institution is only as good as the quality of its teaching staff; they are the heart of the institution producing its graduates, its research products, and its service to the institution, community, and nation (Hayward, 2006). Although institutions for higher education, training, and learning in Kenya produce a considerable proportion of labour force, they remain poorly ranked. Universities are considered to be centres of excellence in education, training, and learning.

The poor situation of teaching staff compounded with their low payments, does not allow them to get committed to providing quality performance. Crude methods of teaching that lecturers use in limited resource environments negatively impact lecturers output, quality of research and publication (UNESCO, 2008). In an open academic environment, the web presence reflects the higher education institutions as a whole. Not only the organization, structure, history or values are included, but the Web is key for all the missions of the university.

Ranking systems of universities exists around the world and still capture further interest and attention of the people for quality assurance and improvement purposes. Internationally both institutions and programme ranking are done by concerned quality assurance agencies as well as the press (Liu & Cheng, 2005). Webometrics ranks institutions of higher learning in the world annually based on openness, impact, presence, and excellence. Webometrics research is based on a correct, comprehensive, deep evaluation of the global university performance (World Bank, 2009).

1.4 Statement of the Problem

Differentiation strategies are marketing techniques used by a firm to establish a strong identity in a specific market; also called segmentation strategy. Using this strategy, a firm will introduce different varieties of the same basic product under the same name into a particular product category and thus cover the range of products available in that category. Differentiation strategy can also be defined as positioning a brand in such a way as to differentiate it from the competition and establish an image that is unique (Hayward, 2006). The commission established the quality guidelines in an attempt to address many questions raised about the standard of university education in Kenya especially with various programmes run by the university. The demand for university education in Kenya has significantly increased and continues to swell. Many qualified students continue to look for opportunities to pursue a university education. This scenario has been considered a revenue stream and a business opportunity for entrepreneurs in private higher education. This has led to the establishment of several private universities in the country. In the midst of the focus on revenue generation by private universities, internal quality assurance practices and specific focus on competitive strategies may have been ignored. This is affirmed by the latest Webometrics worldwide ranking of 2017 that indicates that Strathmore University currently is the best performing private university in Kenya, and is ranked position 6 in Kenya, 162 in Africa and a distant position 4824 in the world. This is an indicator of underperformance. It is not clear, going by the paltry studies on this area, whether differentiated programmes as a competitive strategy adopted by the chartered private universities in Kenya influences their performance. Therefore the current study rides on this academic paucity to interrogate the influence of differentiated programmes on the performance of private universities in Kenya which is the main objective of the study. The study hypothesises that differentiated programmes as a competitive strategy does not influence the performance of private universities in Kenya.

3.0 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a logically developed, described and elaborated network of interrelationships among variables integral in the dynamics of a situation being investigated (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). The study adopted a conceptual framework whose aim is to show how dependent variables are related to the independent variables to keep the research work focused on the objectives of the study. The independent variables are quality management system practices, whereas the dependent variable is university performance measured by

relevant programmes, students graduation rate, students job absorption, patented research, students enrollment and ranking in WebMatrix. The aim of the study is to establish whether internal quality assurance practices adopted have influenced private university performance.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework

4.0 Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive study is concerned with finding out who, what, where and how of the variables of the concerned research. According to Orodho (2002), descriptive survey design as claimed by Luck & Rubin (1992) allows the researcher to gather the information, summarize, present and interpret for the purpose of clarification. The target population for this study comprised of 248 employees working in the Directorate of Quality Assurance in the participating universities, the deans of faculties and schools who gave information on IQA policy content and competitive strategies adopted.

The study models was as follows;

$$(i) Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon$$

Where,

Y = Performance

X₁ = Differentiated Programmes

ε = Random or error term

4.0 Findings and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics on QMS and University Performance

Table 4.1: Differentiation Strategy used by Private Universities

Differentiation Strategy	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Differentiated programmes	29	60	4	2	5
On-line platforms	16	17	2	31	34
School based programmes	32	63	0	2	3
Evening/Weekend classes	42	49	3	2	4
Programmes based on needs	31	44	5	11	9
Industry based programmes	45	39	5	7	4

Source Field Data (2018)

Table 4.11 presents results of differentiation strategy used by private universities in Kenya. Findings on differentiated programmes reveal that majority of respondents 89% agreed that private universities had developed differentiated academic programs compared to 7% who disagreed and 2% who were neutral. Further findings on the online programme as differentiated product reveal that majority of respondents 65% disagreed that private universities have established an online platform for delivery of its academic programs compared to 33% who agreed 2% who were neutral. Findings on school based programme established that majority of respondents 95% agreed that the private universities offered school based programs as a differentiated programme targeting a segment of their market compared to 5% who disagreed. Further findings on

evening/weekend classes established that majority of respondents 91% agreed that private universities had evening / weekend mode of study as differentiated programme compared to 6% who disagreed and 3% who were neutral. Concerning programmes based on industry needs, the study established that majority of respondents 75% agreed that the private universities had developed academic programs based on customer needs compared to 20% who disagreed 5% who were neutral. Findings on the development of industry based programmes established that majority of respondents 84% agreed that private universities had undertaken the development of new academic programs based on market / industry requirements, for example, oil, mining, engineering compared to 11% who disagreed and 5% who were neutral.

This finding indicated that apart from the establishment of differentiated online programmes, private universities in Kenya have employed a differentiation strategy to improve on their performance. Some of the activities carried out to achieve this strategy included; development of differentiated academic programmes, offering school based programs as a differentiated programme targeting a segment of their market, establishing evening / weekend mode of study as a differentiated programme, development of academic programs based on customer and industry needs.

The findings on differentiation strategy are supported by Raduan, Jegak, Haslinda, and Alimin (2009) further affirm that businesses that do things that are distinctive and difficult to replicate have a competitive advantage and are likely to be more profitable than its rivals. Factors such as strategic types, adoption of new technologies, quality products among others, have also been considered to have an important influence on the superior performance of firms. Over the years, business strategies have been found to have a direct influence on firms' competitiveness and growth performance (Sandlberg, 2010).

Findings on developing programmes that meet customers need are supported by the fact that to be effective, the message of differentiation must reach the clients, as the customers' perceptions of the company are important. Dirisu et al. (2013) state that while there are numerous ways to differentiate brands, identifying meaningful product driven differentiators can be especially fruitful in gaining and sustaining a competitive advantage. It is the ability to sell its differentiated product at a price that exceeds what was spent to create it that allows the firm to outperform its rivals and earn above-average returns.

Finding on the differentiated programme is supported by Kamau (2013) who examined the effects of differentiation strategy on sales performance in supermarkets in Nakuru town central business district. The purpose of the study was to establish the effects of differentiation strategy on the sales performance of supermarkets within Nakuru CBD. The study hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between product differentiation strategy adopted by retail supermarkets and sales performance. The study employed a non-experimental research survey design and used purposive and simple random sampling to get the sample size of the respondents. The findings of the study showed that product and physical differentiation play a major role in activating annual sales performance at the supermarkets. The study recommended that supermarkets should scale upon the attributes of the product and physical differentiation strategies if they are to compete in the growing market.

Findings on private universities ability to differentiate their programmes as a means of building a strong brand are supported by The findings from Atikiya et al.'s (2015) study revealed that offering of broad products, building a strong brand reputation within the industry and introduction of innovative products impacted well on manufacturing firm's performance. The researcher recommends that firms are adopting differentiation strategy also need to further look deeper into how to make uniqueness less costly in order to make differentiation a significant practice in the sector. The study by Atikiya et al. was fundamentally based on cost leadership, focus strategies and differentiation strategy. The author used differentiation strategy as a variable and did not

differentiate between product and service differentiation strategy and conclusion was made based on product differentiation.

Differentiated programmes are further supported by Nolega, Oloko, and Oteki (2015) analyzed how product differentiation affects a firm's performance using the Kenya Seed Company as a case study. The study adopted a descriptive research design. Simple random sampling was used in selecting customers and Kenya Seed Company staff while purposive sampling was used in selecting 140 agents. The findings demonstrated how product differentiation influences market dominance using descriptive analysis. The study recommended that the Kenya Seed Company should increase its seed variety according to soil and climatic requirements.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics for Private Universities Performance Indicators

Performance Indicator	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Relevant programmes	60	25	0	9	6
Graduation rate	29	43	16	9	3
Absorption job market	32	57	2	4	5
Patented research and innovation	40	52	1	4	3
Enrollment rate	60	35	0	3	2
Webometric ranking	47	41	2	3	7
Service quality index	48	39	3	6	4

Source: Field Data (2018)

Table 4.13 presents the results of the descriptive statistics for private universities performance indicators. Concerning relevance of the programmes in private universities in Kenya, the study established that majority of respondents 85% agreed that the programmes offered by private universities in Kenya were relevant to job market compared to 15% who disagreed. Findings on graduation rate reveal that majority of respondents 72% agreed that students' graduation rate is high in the private universities compared to 16% who were neutral and 15% who disagreed. Findings on absorption in the job market reveal that the majority of respondents 89% agreed that students absorption to job market was assured compared to 9% who disagreed and 2% who were neutral. Further findings on patented research and innovation reveal that majority of respondents 92% agreed that patented research and innovations are many in private universities in Kenya compared to 7% who disagreed and 1% who were neutral. Findings on enrollment rate reveal that majority of respondents 95% agreed that there was an increasing enrollment in diverse programmes in private universities in Kenya compared to 5% who disagreed. Findings on Webometric Ranking reveal that majority of respondents 88% agreed that private universities in Kenya were well ranked in the webometric ranking compared to 10% who disagreed and 2% who were neutral. Last, findings concerning service quality index reveal that majority of respondents 87% agreed that private universities in Kenya were highly ranked in service quality index compared to 10% who disagreed and 3% who were neutral.

This finding reveals that the performance index of the private universities in Kenya was favourable. This was evident with high performance in the following areas; programmes offered by private universities in Kenya were relevant to the job market. Students' graduation rate is high in the private universities, and their absorption to the job market is assured leading to higher reenrollment rate, favorable ranking in Webometric Ranking and also high service performance index.

Findings on Webometric Ranking is supported by the fact that Universities being an institution for generating and dissemination of knowledge for socio-economic and technological development of a country can be measured in terms of knowledge generated and disseminated worldwide. Such a complex performance measurement is done by third parties like Webometrics and published in the world wide web (Harvey, 2010).

Findings on the ranking of university patents and innovation are supported by the fact that The phenomenon of university rankings has influenced deeply all university systems, even those that were not conceived at first to establish a competitive framework. Therefore, in order to analyze the success or failure of different countries in

their research policy, university systems should be assessed as a whole, and not considering each university as an individual and autonomous unit. Such an approach was applied by Docampo (2011) using the Shanghai Ranking in order to analyze the university systems of the countries represented.

Although when ranked nationally, private universities may be fairly ranked but globally poorly ranked. This is supported by the fact that To be a world-class university in the agricultural science, achieving top 100 of global rankings on agro-subject areas (top 20) and top 100 of global rankings for universities (top 500) is necessary (Liu, 2015). Although institutions of higher education, training, and learning in Kenya produce a considerable proportion of labour force, they remain poorly ranked internationally. Ranking systems of universities exist around the world.

4.2 Test of predictor variable X_1 = Differentiation Strategy

The analyzed variables were; differentiated academic programs, established an online platform, school based programs, evening / weekend mode of study, centralized administration, customized academic programs and new programs based on market needs.

Table 4.2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.385 ^a	.149	.078	.54745

The R value was 0.385 with the R^2 was 0.149, which indicated a low degree of correlation. The R^2 value indicates 14.9% was the R Squared, indicating that the data collected was not closely fitted to the regression line between the independent and dependent variables.

Table 4.3: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.766	6	.628	2.094	.064 ^b
	Residual	21.579	72	.300		
	Total	25.344	78			

Predictors: differentiated academic programs, established online platform, school based programs, evening / weekend mode of study, centralized administration, customized academic programs and new programs based on market needs.

Table 4.27 indicated that the regression model did not predict the outcome variable significantly with $p=0.064$, which was greater than 0.05, and indicated that; overall, the model did not statistically predict the outcome variable.

Table 4.3: Full Regression Model for Differentiation Strategy

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1 (Constant)	2.451	.748		3.279	.002
Differentiated programs	.081	.112	.100	.728	.469
On-line platform	.010	.103	.014	.097	.923
School based programs	.194	.110	.239	1.771	.081
Evening/weekend mode	.112	.126	.137	.893	.375
Customized programs	-.081	.146	-.107	-.554	.581
New programs	.173	.129	.246	1.341	.184

The study established that none of the differentiation strategy use by private universities in Kenya had a relationship with the performance of private universities in Kenya. The fourth hypothesis H_{O4} that Differentiation strategy does not influence the performance of private universities in Kenya, was accepted and the alternate hypothesis H_{A4} : Differentiation strategy influences the performance of private universities in Kenya was rejected.

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

The study established that apart from the establishment of differentiated online programmes, private universities in Kenya have employed a differentiation strategy to improve on their performance. Some of the activities carried out to achieve this strategy included; development of differentiated academic programmes, offering school based programs as a differentiated programme targeting a segment of their market, establishing evening / weekend mode of study as a differentiated programme, development of academic programs based on customer and industry needs. The study established that none of the differentiation strategy use by private universities in Kenya had a relationship with the performance of private universities in Kenya. The hypothesis that Differentiation strategy does not influence the performance of private universities in Kenya was accepted.

First, the study recommends that that private universities in Kenya need to strengthen the quality assurance policy by re-organizing independence of internal quality systems to achieve checks and balances of university operations. Without such systems, it is not easy to gauge universities performance and make the universities fail to achieve their objectives. Secondly, feedback mechanisms of quality assurance reports also need to be enhanced especially developing efficient communication channels and publishing quality audit reports for improvement of university performance. Third, private universities need to enhance their differentiation strategies in order to remain competitive. Programmes should be differentiated; processes also need to be differentiated to make the universities outstanding. Fourth the universities need to carry out more collaborations with international universities and research institutions in order to learn and make their campuses centre of academic excellence.

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